

Evaluation of Blended Fertilizer Rate and Types for better Production of Yield and Yield Components of Sesame (*Sesamum indicum* L.) in Bena-Tsemay District, Southern Ethiopia

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Abstract

Crop and site specific fertilizer recommendation is essential for sustainable crop production. Therefore, a field experiment was conducted in Bena-Tsemay district, Southern Ethiopia, to evaluate blended fertilizer types and rates effect on improving the production of sesame during the main rainy season of 2019 and 2020. A randomized complete block design (RCBD) was employed for the field experiment, with seven treatments representing different combinations of blended fertilizers. Each treatment was replicated three times to ensure statistical validity. The treatments included: Control (no fertilizer), 150kg NPSB + 41kg urea, 160kg NPSZnB + 91kg urea, 200kg NPSB + 72kg urea, 213kg NPSZnB + 122kg urea, 250kg NPSB + 102kg urea and 267kg NPSZnB + 152kg urea. Blended fertilizer application significantly ($p < 0.05$) increased grain yield and aboveground biomass as compared to the control. The maximum and significant grain yield (837.4kg ha^{-1}) and minimum (435.5kg ha^{-1}) were recorded from the application of 160kg NPSZnB + 91 kg ha^{-1} urea and unfertilized treatment, respectively. The application of 160kg NPSZnB + 91 kg ha^{-1} urea had a maximum and acceptable Marginal rate of return (MRR %) and net benefit. Therefore, this type and rate of blended fertilizer can be recommended since it produced a high marginal rate of return, high net benefit, and relatively low total cost of production, for sesame production in the study area and other similar agro-ecologies.

Keywords: Biomass, Blended fertilize, Sesame, Yield.

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Introduction

Sesame (*Sesamum indicum* L.) is a vital oilseed crop cultivated widely in tropical and subtropical regions due to its high nutritional value and economic potential. As a significant source of edible oil, sesame plays a crucial role in food security and rural livelihoods, particularly in developing countries (FAO, 2018). Globally, sesame is produced over an area of 8.8mha^{-1} and annual production around 2.8mt with average productivity of 382kg/ha^{-1} ; whereas, in Africa, average productivity ranges from 300 to 500kg/ha^{-1} in pure stand; but under good management it reaches as high as 3000kg/ha^{-1} (Kafriti and Deckers, 2001).

In Ethiopia, sesame is one of the most important cash crops, contributing to the economy through both domestic consumption and export (Bishaw *et al.*, 2019). Despite its importance, sesame productivity in Ethiopia has been constrained by various factors, including inadequate soil fertility and improper fertilizer management. Many farmers rely on traditional farming practices, which often result in suboptimal yields. Research indicates that the use of balanced fertilizers can significantly enhance crop growth and productivity by addressing nutrient deficiencies in the soil (Oladapo *et al.*, 2018). Specifically, blended

fertilizers that combine nitrogen, phosphorus, sulfur, and micronutrients have been shown to improve sesame yields and overall economic returns (Zhang *et al.*, 2021).

In Ethiopia, sesame is commonly cultivated in areas ranging in altitude from 500 to 1300 m above sea level in rain-fed condition. The low lands of Ethiopia adjoining the Sudan are the traditional sesame growing areas. In 2014, there was a total of 420,495 ha¹ sesame land cultivated by about 867,347 smallholder farmers in Tigray, Amhara, Oromia, Benishangul-Gumuz and SNNP regions and 276,701 ha¹ of sesame land cultivated by medium and large commercial farms in Tigray, Amhara, Oromia, Benishangul-Gumuz, SNNP, Afar, Gambella regions (CSA, 2012).

Fertilizers are the foremost important inputs for increasing the productivity of crops (Prasad, 2009). Fertilizer trials have been conducted for a couple of decades on various crops elsewhere in Ethiopia. Consequently, yield and biomass production improvements for various crop types have been reported by different scholars (Amsal *et al.*, 2000; Fanuel and Gifole, 2013 and Okalebo *et al.*, 2001). Beside this there was argument sesame responds poorly to fertilizer, but it is very difficult to reconcile this statement with the plant performance on fertile and infertile soil in any given area. Therefore, this activity is tent to initiate to overcome these problems. In Bena-Tsemay, the application of blended fertilizers has not been extensively studied. This region's unique agro-ecological conditions present an opportunity to evaluate how different fertilizer combinations influence sesame yield and economic performance. The objectives of this study were to assess the effects of varying rates and types of blended fertilizers on sesame yield parameters and to perform a marginal analysis of the economic viability of these studies. The findings from this research aim to provide insights into effective fertilizer management strategies that can enhance sesame production, thereby supporting the sustainability and profitability of smallholder farmers in the study area.

Materials and Methods

Description of the Study Area

Figure 1. Map of the Study Area

The study was conducted in Bena Tsemay district, a study area characterized by its unique agro-climatic conditions suitable for sesame cultivation. The area was selected due to its historical production of sesame and the opportunity to evaluate the effects of blended fertilizers on yield and economic performance. A

field experiment was conducted on 2019 and 2020 and geographically it located 36°.59.037' E longitude and 5°.23.238'N latitude. The particular site, Enchete kebele is located about 82 km East of Jinka town. At an altitude of 526 meters asl. It is characterized by flat land features. The property of the soil is sandy loam. The annual average rainfall of the district ranges between 601 to 1600 mm. The minimum and maximum annual temperature of 27.5°C and 37.5°C, respectively. The study area has diversity of climate, soil, and land forms. The topography of the district includes mountains, hills, uplands and lowland plains. The district generally experiences two cropping seasons namely belg and meher.

Experimental Design and Treatments

A randomized complete block design (RCBD) was employed for the experiment, with seven treatments representing different combinations of blended fertilizers. Each treatment was replicated three times to ensure statistical validity. The treatments included: Control (no fertilizer), 150kg NPSB + 41kg urea, 160kg NPSZnB + 91kg urea, 200kg NPSB + 72kg urea, 213kg NPSZnB + 122kg urea, 250kg NPSB + 102kg urea and 267kg NPSZnB + 152kg urea. The fertilizers used were nitrogen-phosphorus-sulfur blends (NPSB) and zinc-boron (ZnB) formulations, which were selected based on soil nutrient analysis and the specific needs of sesame plants (Tekalign, 1991).

Table 1. Detail of Treatment Set Up

Treatment in Compound form	Elemental Content of Nutrient (kg ^{ha} ⁻¹)					
	N	P ₂ O ₅	S	B	Zn	K
Control	0	0	0	0	0	0
150 kg ^{ha} ⁻¹ NPSB + 41 kg ^{ha} ⁻¹ urea	46	56.5	10.4	0.15	0	60
200 kg ^{ha} ⁻¹ NPSB + 72 kg ^{ha} ⁻¹ urea	69	75.4	13.9	0.2	0	60
250 kg ^{ha} ⁻¹ NPSB + 102 kg ^{ha} ⁻¹ urea	92	94.25	17.25	0.25	0	60
160 kg ^{ha} ⁻¹ NPSZnB + 91 kg ^{ha} ⁻¹ urea	69	56.68	11.8	0.16	3.52	60
213 kg ^{ha} ⁻¹ NPSZnB + 122 kg ^{ha} ⁻¹ urea	92	73.5	15.85	0.21	4.68	60
267 kg ^{ha} ⁻¹ NPSZnB + 152 kg ^{ha} ⁻¹ urea	111	91.12	19.89	0.26	5.87	60

All sources of fertilizers were applied in the form of Urea and blended form. Recommended doses of blended fertilizers were applied at planting while nitrogen was split twice: half was applied at planting and the remainder was applied 30 days after planting in all treatments except control (untreated) plots. The variety Mehando-80 sesame was chosen based on the results of adaptation evaluation trial conducted on the study area.

Crop Management

Sesame seeds were sown following standard agronomic practices. The plant were thinned two weeks after germination when the seedling attained 15cm to keep intra raw spacing 10cm, irrigation was given to six days interval during early stage and slightly decreased at maturity up to 10 days. Pre-planting soil testing was conducted to assess nutrient levels and determine baseline soil health. Fertilizers were applied based on the recommended rates and were incorporated into the soil at planting. Irrigation and pest management practices were standardized across all treatments to minimize variability.

Soil Sampling and Analysis

Composite soil sample was collected before planting in zigzag movement with the sampling depth of (0-20) cm. Collected soil samples were analyzed for soil texture, pH, %OC and %TN following the procedure of air dry and grinding then passing through 2mm sieve in laboratory. Soil pH of the soils was measured potentiometrically in water suspension to 1:2.5 (soil:water ratio). Total nitrogen was determined by the Kjeldahl method and soil organic carbon (OC) content was used by the wet digestion method.

Data Collection

Data on yield parameters, including plant height, number of branches, and number of pods/capsules per plant, biomass, and yield were recorded at physiological maturity. Harvesting was conducted at physiological maturity, and yield and biomass was calculated as kilograms per hectare.

Statistical Analysis

Data were analyzed using R Software, and the significance of differences among treatments was assessed using analysis of variance (ANOVA). Mean comparisons were made using the least significant difference (LSD) test at a 5% significance level (Hassan *et al.*, 2022).

Economic analysis

Economic analysis was performed by calculating total revenue (TR), total variable costs (TVC), gross margin (GM), and net return (NR) for each treatment. Marginal analysis was applied to evaluate the marginal rate of return (MRR) of each treatment (Jalal *et al.*, 2020). To estimate economic parameters, the total yield was valued based on average market price collected from the local markets during two consecutive years of production. The average cost of urea, KCl, NPSZnB and NPSB were 14.79, 15.46, 15.48 and 15.48 Birr per kg respectively. A wage rate of 50 birr a man per day was considered.

Results and Discussion

Soil Analysis before Planting

The soil analysis results prior to planting reveal essential parameters influencing plant growth (Table 2). The particle size distribution indicates a predominance of sand (62%), with silt (18%) and clay (20%), classifying the soil as sandy loam. This texture typically promotes good drainage and aeration, favoring root development and microbial activity (Hillel, 2004). The soil pH is recorded at 7.76, categorizing it as moderately alkaline. This pH level is conducive for most crops, as it supports nutrient availability while minimizing potential toxicities associated with highly acidic soils (Haq *et al.*, 2020).

Table 2. Selected Physicochemical Properties of the Experimental Site before Planting

Soil Parameter	Value	Rating	Reference
Particle size distribution (%)			
Sand	62		
Silt	18		
Clay	20		
Textural class		Sandy loam	Soil texture triangle
pH (1:2.5)	7.76	Moderately Alkaline	Tekalign (1991)
%OC	1.56	Moderate	Tekalign (1991)
%TN	0.03	Very low	Tekalign (1991)

Note: OC: Organic Carbon; TN: Total Nitrogen

Organic carbon (OC) content is measured at 1.56%, which is considered moderate (Tekalign, 1991). Organic carbon plays a critical role in soil fertility and structure, affecting nutrient retention and microbial biodiversity (Lal, 2016). However, the total nitrogen (TN) level is notably low at 0.03%. Low nitrogen levels can limit plant growth, emphasizing the need for amendments to enhance fertility prior to planting (Brady & Weil, 2010). These results underline the necessity for strategic soil management practices, including the addition of organic matter and nitrogen sources, to optimize soil health and crop productivity in the study area.

Number of Branches and Cups

The yield and yield parameters of sesame were significantly influenced by varying applications of inorganic fertilizers, as indicated in Table 3. The number of branches per plant ranged from 6.2 in the control treatment to 7.3 in 160kg NPSZnB + 91 kg urea, which received the optimum rate of NPSZnB and urea. This increase in branch number is likely attributed to improved nutrient availability, promoting vegetative growth (Khan et al., 2020). In contrast, the other all treatments, while exhibiting slight increases in branches, did not significantly differ from the control, suggesting a threshold effect of nutrient application beyond which additional fertilizers yield diminishing returns.

Similarly, the number of cups per plant also showed variability across treatments, with the highest count (116.2) observed in application of 267kg NPSZnB + 152 kg urea ha⁻¹. The consistent increase in cup number with higher fertilizer applications suggests enhanced reproductive development, which is critical for yield maximization (Ghosh *et al.*, 2019).

Plant Height and Biomass

Plant height remained relatively stable across treatments, with a maximum of 1.48 m recorded in 200 kg NPSB+72 kg urea ha⁻¹. This parameter, while important, did not significantly correlate with yield, as indicated by the statistically similar heights across several treatments. The biomass yield (Biom/to/ha) ranged from 3.9 in the control to 6.8 in 213kg NPSZnB + 122 kg urea, with 160kg NPSZnB + 91 kg urea application also achieving a high biomass of 6.1. The increases in biomass align with findings that optimal fertilizer application enhances overall plant vigor and productivity (Zhang et al., 2018).

Yield

The grain yield exhibited the most pronounced differences among treatments. The highest yield of 837.4 kg/ha was obtained with the application of 160kg NPSZnB + 91kg urea, indicating that the combination of 160 kg NPSZnB and 91 kg urea effectively met the nutritional demands of sesame. This result underscores the importance of balanced fertilization in achieving high yields, as nutrient deficiencies can severely limit crop performance (Khan et al., 2020; Ghosh et al., 2019). Conversely, the control treatment yielded only 435.5 kg/ha, illustrating the significant impact of fertilizer on productivity. The results suggest that the appropriate application of inorganic fertilizers, particularly NPSZnB combined with urea, can significantly enhance sesame yield and its associated parameters.

Table 3. Yield and Yield Parameters of Sesame Influenced by Inorganic Fertilizer Application at Bena Tsemay (2018 and 2019)

Treatment	N bra	N cup	PH (m)	Biom (t/ha)	GY kg/ha
T1 Control (untreated)	6.2 ^b	72.7 ^b	1.43 ^{ab}	3.9 ^c	435.5 ^c
T2 150 kg NPSB+41 kg urea	6.4 ^{ab}	81.5 ^{ab}	1.43 ^{ab}	4.6 ^b	568.5 ^b
T3 200 kg NPSB+72 kg urea	6 ^b	83.6 ^{ab}	1.48 ^a	5.3 ^{ab}	625.8 ^{ab}
T4 250 kg NPSB+102 kg urea	6.9 ^{ab}	82.8 ^{ab}	1.42 ^{ab}	5.2 ^{ab}	535.4 ^{bc}
T5 160kgNPSZnB + 91 kg urea	7.3 ^a	86.6 ^{ab}	1.35 ^{ab}	6.1 ^{ab}	837.4 ^a
T6 213 kgNPSZnB + 122 kg urea	6.8 ^{ab}	116.2 ^a	1.45 ^{ab}	6.8 ^a	739.6 ^{ab}
T7 267 kgNPSZnB + 152 kg urea	6.2 ^b	77.8 ^b	1.34 ^b	5.2 ^{ab}	543.9 ^{bc}
LSD (5%)	0.6	34	7.9	1	150.6
CV (%)	9	22	4.7	15	21
Mean	6.5	85	1.41	5.7	612.3

Note: Mean values with different letters within the column are statistically different at $\alpha \leq 5\%$. N bra= number of branch per plant, N cup= number of cups, PH = plant height and GY = grain yield/ha

Economic Analysis

The partial budget analysis of sesame is significantly affected by the application of NPSB, and NPSZnB (Table 4). Gross margin varied significantly across treatments, with 160 kg NPSZnB + 91 kg urea yielding the maximum revenue of 30,146.4 ETB/ha. This reflects the impact of optimal fertilizer application on sesame yield, confirming previous studies that highlight the relationship between appropriate fertilization and increased crop profitability (Oladapo et al., 2018). Conversely, the control treatment generated the lowest revenue at 15,678 ETB/ha, underscoring the economic disadvantage of minimal fertilization (Davis et al., 2019).

Net return further elucidate the economic viability of each treatment. 160 kg NPSZnB + 91 kg urea not only achieved the highest revenue but also exhibited a substantial net return of 19,511.74 ETB/ha. This indicates that, despite the costs involved, the investment in blended fertilizers resulted in significant profitability. In comparison, with no fertilizer investment, yielded a net return of (15,678 ETB/ha), underlining its inefficacy for profitable farming (Jalal et al., 2020). While 200kg NPSB + 72kg urea also demonstrated strong economic performance with a net benefit of 11,633.02 ETB/ha, 250kg NPSB + 102kg urea showed a decline in profitability due to higher costs relative to returns, resulting in a lower net return of 7,161.28 ETB/ha. This suggests that there is an optimal range for fertilizer application beyond which additional inputs may not yield proportional returns (Hassan et al., 2022).

Table 4. The Economic Performance of Sesame under Blended Fertilizer Rate and Type in Benatsemay

Treatments	10% adi yield	GM (ETB)	TVC (ETB)	NR (ETB)
Control (untreated)	391.95	15678	0	15678
150 kg NPSB+41 kg urea	511.65	20466	9663	10803
200 kg NPSB+72 kg urea	563.22	22528.8	10895.78	11633.02
250 kg NPSB+102 kg urea	481.86	19274.4	12113.12	7161.28
160kgNPSZnB + 91 kg urea	753.66	30146.4	10634.66	19511.74
213 kgNPSZnB + 122 kg urea	665.64	26625.6	11951	14674.6
267 kgNPSZnB + 152 kg urea	489.51	19580.4	13263.53	6316.87

Note: TVC: Total variable cost (ETB/ha), GM: Gross margin (ETB/ha) and NR: Net return (ETB/ha)

Dominance analysis reveals which treatments are economically superior based on net benefits and costs. Most of the applied treatments were marked as dominated (D), indicating they provided lower net benefits relative to their costs compared to 160kg NPSZnB + 91kg urea. This reinforces the effectiveness of the 160kg NPSZnB + 91kg urea treatment, which stands out as a dominant for achieving higher economic returns.

The marginal rate of return (MRR) is an essential indicator of the efficiency of additional investment in fertilizers. 160kg NPSZnB + 91kg urea recorded an impressive MRR of 896%, suggesting that each additional unit of currency invested in this treatment yields nearly nine times the return. This high MRR underscores the critical role of balanced nutrient application in maximizing profitability in sesame production (Davis *et al.*, 2019). In contrast, the treatments deemed dominated did not provide favorable MRRs, reflecting diminishing returns on increased fertilizer use. This indicates the importance of optimizing input use to avoid unnecessary expenditure and to enhance economic sustainability (Jalal *et al.*, 2020).

Overall, the findings from this economic analysis indicate that the application of blended fertilizers can significantly enhance the economic performance of sesame cultivation. Application of 160kg NPSZnB + 91kg urea not only improve yield but also maximize profitability, thus supporting the recommendation for optimized fertilizer use in sesame farming to achieve sustainable agricultural practices. The marginal

analysis indicates that the application of 160kg NPSZnB + 91kg urea is the most economically viable option for sesame production in Bena Tsemay, offering the highest net benefits and an exceptional MRR. These findings suggest that targeted fertilizer applications can significantly enhance the profitability of sesame cultivation while emphasizing the need for careful management of input costs to maximize economic outcomes.

Table 5. Marginal Analysis of Sesame under Blended Fertilizer Rate and Type in Bena Tsemay

Treatments	variables			
	TVC(ETB/ha)	NB (ETB/ha)	DA	MRR (%)
Control	0	15678	-	
150 kgha ⁻¹ NPSB + 41kg urea	9663	10803	D	
160 kgha ⁻¹ NPSBZn + 91 kg urea	10634.66	19511.74	ND	896
200 kgha ⁻¹ NPSB + 72 kg urea	10895.78	11633.02	D	
213 kgha ⁻¹ NPSZn + 122 kg urea	11951	14674.6	D	
250 kgha ⁻¹ NPSB + 102 kg urea	12113.12	7161.28	D	
267 kgha ⁻¹ NPSZnB + 152 kg urea	13263.53	6316.87	D	

Note: TVC= Total variable cost, NB= Net benefit, DA= Dominant Analysis, MRR= Marginal rate of return

Conclusion and Recommendation

Application of blended fertilizer types and rates indicated significant differences on yield and yield parameters of sesame. The current study revealed that the maximum grain yield of 837.4kg ha⁻¹ was recorded from the plots received 160 kgha⁻¹ NPSZnB + 91kg urea (69N, 56.68P₂O₅, 60K, 11.8S, 0.16B and 3.52Zn) ha⁻¹ of blended fertilizer application. The partial budget analysis also indicated that the maximum net benefit (19511.74 ETB ha⁻¹) with acceptable marginal rate of return (MRR %) 896% was recorded from the application of 160 kgha⁻¹ NPSZnB + 91kg urea (69N, 56.68P₂O₅, 60K, 11.8S, 0.16B and 3.52Zn) ha⁻¹ blended fertilizer. Application of 160kg NPSZnB + 91kg urea not only improve yield but also maximize profitability, thus supporting the recommendation for optimized fertilizer use in sesame farming to achieve sustainable agricultural practices. Thus, based on the grain yield and economic analysis, the application of 160 kgha⁻¹ NPSZnB + 91kg urea blended fertilizer can be recommended for Bena-Tsemay district and other areas with similar agro-ecology and soil conditions. However, to reach at a further recommendation, further investigations are needed each nutrients omission and commission and blended fertilizer formulation types.

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